

An Academic Look at the History of Education Administration

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Abstract

John Dewey issued a cautionary statement in 1902: "It is easy to fall into the habit of viewing the mechanics of school organization and administration as something relatively external and indifferent to educational ideals" (Dewey, 1902: 22, 23). The history of educational leadership and management as a field of study and practice lends credence to its reservations. With a few notable exceptions, the field has traditionally been built on the principle of maintaining a clear separation between management theory and educational concerns. Additionally, the field is characterized by an emphasis on operational aspects of school management. The official study of educational administration and teaching began in the United States in the early years of the twentieth century. It began with the appointment of men like George Strayer at College Columbia, Paul Hanus at Harvard, and Edward Elliot at Wisconsin. Bobbit in Chicago and, perhaps most importantly, Ellwood in Stanford. These men were among the first to teach and study educational

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administration in an academic setting. Cubberly had limited experience in teaching, as her own studies and career focused on geology and physical sciences. However, this is "school management, school problems, school organization, school statistics, secondary schools, history of education, the relationship of illiteracy and crime to education, etc." (Tyack and Hansot, 1982: 124). He served as superintendent of schools in San Diego for two years, during which time he realized that school boards in the city needed to be non-political. There is no doubt that this experience played a role in bringing some of these ideas to mind. In this regard, his views agreed with those of the growing Reform Movement. This movement was dedicated to the consolidation of smaller public institutions, such as schools and school districts, into larger institutional structures that were hierarchically structured and controlled from a central location. In this respect, his views coincided with those of the movement.

Keywords: *Educational Administration, Education of Trainers, Schools in Educational Administration, History of Educational Administration*

Introduction

The paradigm used was that of a large industrial enterprise, whose operations were guided by a recent development of management science. When this new science of management was applied to the public sphere, he separated administrative concerns from political ones, saying that "...management is outside the proper sphere of politics." Administrative concerns are not political concerns" (Woodrow Wilson, 1887: 97).

By 1930, the transformation of American city government, along with the management of schools, succeeded in displacing local political interests and creating a series of professionalized bureaucracies subordinate to national organizations supported by systematic professional training and a national network of influential individuals. This resulted in the creation of a series of interconnected professionalized bureaucracies in national organizations. Strayer, for example, concluded that "significant progress in the management of city school systems over the past twenty-five years has been due primarily to two reasons." This is because, according to Strayer, there has been "significant progress in the management of city school systems." First, the application of the scientific approach to management issues, and second, the vocational training

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of school administrators" (Tyack and Hansot, 1982: 152). Strayer's teachers Carter Alexander, a colleague at the College, summarized the administrative progressives' view of the purpose of educational research as follows: "Discovering the most efficient procedures in the light of generally accepted educational objectives, organization, supervision, financing and evaluation of the educational service program" (Tyack and Hansot, 1982: 153).

This is how administrative progressives see the purpose of educational research. This agenda, carried to its logical conclusion, gave rise to what Callaghan (1962) called the "cult of efficiency." It was a cult built on the assumption that there was general consensus on the aims of education and was later ignored in favor of the pursuit of effective management. On the basis of the Principles of Scientific Management first proposed by Taylor (1911), leadership in education came to be defined as the process of obtaining the highest possible level of effectiveness from educational resources, including both physical and human assets. This job-management view of educational leadership has dominated the evolving university-based training programs in education management. This idea of educational leadership has been championed and widely popularized by prominent figures such as Strayer, Cubberly, and Bobbit. In addition, a new professional elite of university-educated administrators sought to replace Tammany Hall of local politics and nepotism, while simultaneously creating a national "educational Tammany Hall" for themselves and their protégés, Strayer - Englehardt. Tammany Hall, New York seems very weak" (Tyack and Hansot, 1982: 141).

Through the establishment of new university programs, national associations (both public and private) and networks of political influence in key school districts, this education foundation has succeeded in reforming education from the top down.

As a result, a new meritocracy of administrative progressives was able to be established and sponsorship and patronage applied in the creation of new educational elites, a significant shift in leadership across the education system, leading to the merging of many small local school districts with larger ones, the imposition of the activities of scientific management on teachers, the consolidation of central schools. led to

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Methodology

It was decided to put a scientific cover on a number of methods and practices that were by no means scientific, and an atmosphere that had already pervaded anti-intellectualism became much more common (1962: 246). Of course, the most prominent among those who opposed this change was John Dewey (Dewey, 1902, 1916). Others also expressed their opposition to this change. On the other hand, the conflict was not just a battle of ideas. The educational oligarchy that arose as a result of recourse to scientific management and management. The formation of the professionally trained managerial staff consists predominantly of men.

In fact, while one of the aims of scientific management was to separate the concept from practice and enhance managerial privileges (Edwards, 1979), the use of scientific management in education was aimed at separating largely male administrators from female instructors. Ella, who offered leadership to women's unions as superintendent of the Chicago School District and a staunch advocate of women's advancement into positions of authority in the teaching profession. Women like Flagg Young objected. One battleground for women's defiance of the male oligarchy was the National Education Association (NEA), where Margaret Haley led an attack on the male old guard and its centralist tendencies.

Data

He argued that the male elder guard's intention was to "despotism our entire school system" (Tyack and Hansot, 1982: 186). Attempts by female teachers to expand participatory structures within the NEA met with some success, but were eventually repulsed by male leading members such as Charles Eliot. Eliot's patronizing attitude is noted in his comment that women like Young and Haley exhibit "a general moral ignorance or inadequacy that tends to be manifest whenever they act in political, social, or educational contexts" (Tyack and Hansot, 1982: 186). Young and Haley, on the other hand, advocated a leadership style consistent with Dewey's understanding that a democratic education is essential to sustaining a democratic society. They didn't just want more women's participation in management and leadership; rather, they were fighting for that kind of leadership. Their demand was a specific form of educational leadership that would "make it the essential tool for helping children and adolescents acquire citizenship in a government designed

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to be by all and for all" (Young, 1916: 6). In this they called for the return of politics to educational leadership and the recognition that educational ideals are indeed an integral part of political and educational leadership.

They also struggled for recognition that educational ideals were an inevitable aspect of educational leadership. The inextricable links between politics and education were demonstrated through the leadership of teachers like Leonard Covello, whose political agitation in East Harlem led to the founding of Benjamin Franklin High School and his appointment as its first principal. The Trust sought efficiency in the management of increasingly large-scale urban school systems and insisted that education is an activity best left to the professionals. Covello believed that the school should be able to accommodate the many cultural backgrounds of the student body and serve as a center for mobilizing communities in the name of social justice. Learning would occur through active participation in the community, and politics and learning, democracy and social justice would be defined through action (Covello, 1936, 1958; Peebles, 1978). Learning would take place through active participation in the community.

was not as important as displaying leadership by helping articulate democratic demands through learning and social action in the very Deweyan pursuit of social justice. Meanwhile, in the academic world, a new generation of professors has become increasingly concerned with the disparagement of education and educational leadership by their real-life peers as they pursue their research on school finances and effective management using survey techniques. These true science department colleagues saw education and educational leadership as non-scientific pursuits. As a direct result of this, there was a trend towards the use of concepts derived from the social sciences, particularly psychology and sociology. Jacob Gentzel's, a psychologist at the University of Chicago, Andrew Halpin, a member of the Ohio State University Staff Research Board, and Columbia Teachers at College Daniel Griffiths, an iconoclastic management professor, was among the influential cadres who initiated what was to come next.

From the literature

It is known as the Theory Movement in educational administration in the 1950s. On the basis of a commitment to logical positivism, these scholars criticized the non-theoretical character of

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research in educational administration. They then started a process of developing an approach that was both theory-bound and expressed through research design adapted from emerging social sciences (Culbertson, 1988). The Theory Movement took the depoliticization of educational leadership a step further by pursuing a values-free management science. Through the study of what is rather than what ought to be, this value-free management science will reveal a series of empirically grounded hypothetical-deductive propositions that can form the basis of an appropriate positivist science of management. This was achieved by shifting the focus from what should be to what is. This was considered a comprehensive management philosophy, where educational administration is only a specific practice. The Kellogg Foundation has funded the establishment of eight university-based centers as part of the Program for Collaboration in Educational Administration. These centers can be found in the following locations:

It was tasked with developing science-based programs for the training of educational administrators, producing new literature on educational administration, and supporting the establishment of professional organizations committed to a new approach to educational administration and leadership (Moore, 1964). The end result was to establish behavioral science and systems theory as the theoretical foundations of educational administration and leadership.

Gentzel's 'A psycho-sociological framework for the study of educational administration' (1952), the foundation for the Theory Movement was laid on the adoption of Parsonian systems theory. This laid the groundwork for the development of the Theory Movement. In this section, various social system abstractions such as the individual, personality, and need dispositions as well as institutions, roles, and expectations, as well as the nomothetic and ideographic dimensions of social behavior, are developed into a theoretical systematic series. The 1964 National Student Engagement Survey (NSSE) yearbook (Behavioral Science and Educational Administration; Griffiths, 1964) showed how pervasive systems theory and associated abstractions have become. Therefore, more normative issues were removed from leadership, and the study of leadership evolved into research and classification of how leaders behave independently of ethical concerns about what they should do (Halpin, 1958: 6).

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The study of leadership has become the study and classification of how leaders behave. The Theory Movement sought to build a science of management and leadership behavior, while the Theory Movement pursued its theoretical abstractions on which to build a science of management and leadership behavior. Brown - Board of Education decision made ten years before the 1964 NSSE Yearbook was published; however, the Annual does not mention a single word about the impact of the decision on the field of educational administration and leadership.

Not to mention the educational leadership in Southern states, which closed nearly all black schools and fired 38,000 black teachers and administrators (Hudson and Holmes, 1994; Anderson, 2006) (Hudson and Holmes, 1994; Anderson, 2006). There is not a single member of the Theory Movement on the list of social scientists who signed the report written by black psychologist Kenneth B. Clark. This work was crucial in the decision on Brown against the Board of Education. As early as 1960, Andrew Halpin pointed to the inconsistency between management theory and the real world of school management when he made the following observation about the Theory Movement: "There is clearly a gap. The problem is that the theoretical models of management developed by scientists are too logical, too organized. and very sterile . . . we must take a fresh look at our current points of view" (1960: 284). This was a sentiment echoed by Schwab (1964) (Culbertson, 1988: 19).

[Increasing Demand for University Courses in Educational Administration](#)

This was due, at least in part, to the large increase in the number and overall size of secondary schools in the postwar period. The situation was everywhere, not just on the North American continent.

Educational administration courses were opened in Great Britain at the Institute of Education (University of London), Bristol, Birmingham and Oxford under the leadership of Ray Bolam, Meredydd Hughes, Eric Hoyle, Len Watson, William Taylor, George Baron. Educational administration courses were conducted in Australia by Bill Walker at the University of New England and by Bill Bassett and Mac Grassie at the University of Queensland. In Canada, educational administration courses were led by Robin Farquhar at the OISE and the Arts are important despite widespread consensus in the Commonwealth of Nations that the social sciences are a useful source of theory and methodology for educational administration (Walker et al., 1973;

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Baron et al. Taylor), 1969; Greenfield, 1968), traditions of analysis in the Commonwealth of Nations differed somewhat from those in the United States.

There was general agreement that the social sciences were a useful source of theory and methodology for educational administration. In Great Britain, for example, the historical traditions of the headmaster, as well as their political and religious functions, have had a significant impact. This should come as no surprise given the important role England's major public schools have played in the country's history (Baron, 1970; Bernbaum, 1976). In fact, according to Bamford (1957), the success or failure of the principal in many cases determined not only the future of schools but also the future of the entire society. For example, in a town of less than 8,000 inhabitants, Marlborough the College has a student body of around 800 students and generates an annual revenue of around GBP 22 million.

Argument

In the past, the role of the principal in such schools (Peters, 1976) formed the basis of the great man theory of leadership. This theory suggested that autonomy, authority, religion, and morality collectively define a very strong role for the principal. This concept was perhaps best expressed by Thring of Uppingham, who said, "I am superior here and will not accept any interference" (cited in Bernbaum, 1976: 34). According to Cannon (1970), the principalship was a forum where issues related to religion, social class and politics were discussed in ways that shape the concepts of educational administration and leadership. Control of the curriculum, with its ties to religion and the division of classes, was essential to the realization of this ideal. According to Gordon (1974), the history of schooling in England was a history of class warfare: "No educational plan will be considered satisfactory by the middle class that does not ensure that their children are completely separated from those in the other classes." a separation as complete as that between the lower class and the children of the upper classes. relentlessly shaped by its policies to expand access forever (Baron, 1969).

In such an environment, school administration's policies were essential to an understanding of educational administration and administration, as Hoyle (1986) pointed out. Both Canada (Robinson and Elliott, 1973) and Australia (Partridge, 1968) held views similar to those presented here. A similar viewpoint has long been common in New Zealand (Webb, 1937; Parkyn, 1954) and

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was quoted by Currie in 1962. In his speech to the International Interview Program in Bristol, those from the Commonwealth largely supported the view that organizational theory, based on the twin support of behavioral theory and systems theory, is an inadequate and misleading description of schools as organizations (Greenfield, 1975). Greenfield's speech was given at the International Interview Program in Bristol. The basic premises on which the Theory Movement was built were being attacked, and these premises had to be sustained as vigorously as possible. The following decade can be seen as an attempt to support both the remnants of the Theory Movement through texts such as Hoy and Miskel (1978) and Silver (1983) that continue to separate education from management and follow the science of the latter. This is important as a basis for exploration of alternative theoretical approaches as a basis for education management teaching, as well as an attempt to compensate for the feeling that education administrators are not adequately prepared for their position. Glatter's observation was confirmed to be correct when Hoy and Miskel (1978) and Silver (1983) published the Handbook of Research on Education Management (Boyan, 1988) in 1988. an astonishing narrow-mindedness that ignores it.

Both of these features were present. As Walker points out, despite the United Education Administration Council's (UCEA) support for the establishment of education management societies. The United Kingdom, Australia, Canada and New Zealand, as well as their umbrella body, the Commonwealth Education Administration Council, and its access to Africa, the Caribbean and Cyprus, and the ensuing stream of research and writing, the United States of America, characterized by "narcissism and elitism". He continued to pursue scholarships in the field of educational administration. The decade of the 1980s witnessed the emergence of a wide variety of new perspectives (Sergio Anni and Corbally, 1984) Sergio Anni did everything he could to promote the adoption of a cultural perspective in educational institutions. Greenfield's subjectivist perspective was further developed (Greenfield and Ribbins, 1993; Macmillan, 2003). Foster (1987) outlined a strategy based on critical theory, and it was Smyth and colleagues (Smyth, 1989) who later developed it. Bates (1980, 1983, 1987) established an approach based on the new sociology of education. He called for the correction of the separation of the concepts of education and administration, and also demanded that educational administration be informed by ideas of social justice. Bates' approach was a call to inform educational administration with concepts of social justice. Gronn (1986) was an advocate of the use of micropolitical theory and psychological

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views in the management of educational institutions. Leithwood (1982) was the one who linked educational leadership to the process of deciding on a curriculum. Fullan (1982) was the person who made the link between leadership and educational reform. In their article "Educational Leadership in the Context of Educational Reform" (Jacobsen and Conway, 1990), Stephen Jacobsen and colleagues argue that educational leadership should be understood in the context of educational reform. In fact, there was an influx of ideas, and by the early 1990s Donmoyer, Scheurich and their colleagues in the USA were developing an entirely new postpositivist perspective. This perspective aimed to construct a new approach to theory, to create a very different knowledge base for educational administration, and to incorporate previously excluded voices, particularly those related to gender and race (Donmoyer et al., 1995). perspective has also been developed.

The decade of the 1990s witnessed a further expansion of perspective that included important work around the local administration of schools as a practical response to concerns in educational administration (Caldwell and Spinks, 1992; Wallace, 1992).

In addition, there was a recent attempt to reassert the centrality of educational issues as a central focus of educational leadership (Duignan and Macpherson, 1992). In their work, Crump (1993) and colleagues placed school-centered leadership against the background of chaotic social and political change in both national and international settings. Hodgkinson (1991) expanded on his earlier thoughts on educational leadership as a kind of moral art. Ribbins and Marland's (1994) use of biography as a method of understanding leadership was revived. The concept of dramaturgical analysis was applied to leadership by Starratt (1990). Evers and Lakomski (1995) supported the use of a consistent methodology when discussing the theory. A feminist perspective on educational leadership has been developed by Blackmore, Blackmore, and Kenway and Hall (Blackmore, 1999; Blackmore and Kenway 1993; Hall 1996). Blackmore's work can be found in Blackmore, Blackmore and Kenway 1993 and Hall 1996. Begley and colleagues developed a values framework for school management and published it in 1999 under the title Begley and Leonard. Grace (1995) presented a policy knowledge-based approach to school leadership. Gronn (1999) presented an educational leadership review that takes into account the requirements of the new global order. Sergioivanni (1999) undertakes a second round of rethinking about educational leadership and the concept of school as a contractual community. The organizational development

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approach to schools was first pioneered in Australia by Mulford and collaborators (Mulford and Kendall, 1975; Mulford et al., 1977; Mulford, 1978). Schmuck and Runkel (1995) are credited for solidifying this approach to school management and leadership. The shift in focus from management to management and then from management to leadership is one of the things that stands out most about the diversity of methods followed. Throughout its history, the origins of the field can be traced back to its current emphasis on management, then management, and finally leadership. This shift is exemplified by the British Educational Administration Association and its journals changing their names over the last three decades from Educational Administration in the 1970s to Educational Administration and Administration in the 1980s and 1990s, and Educational Administration, Administration in the 1980s and 1990s. Leadership in the current decade of the 2000s. The change in emphasis has been quite significant, as leadership is emerging as the most important issue at the moment. Although the name of Tomlinson's (2004) encyclopedic article collection is Educational Administration, the classification of these articles is formed by four basic concepts:

[Educational Ideals, Theory, Leadership and Change](#)

An example of this can be found in the study of Tomlinson (2004). Its arrangement is quite different in this respect from, for example, Boyan's 1988 Handbook of Educational Administration Studies. Tomlinson's collection is a retrospective of the field. There is a significant concern about transforming the educational context; the impact of globalization and the demands of the new economy; the social aims of schools and the impact of the market economy; learning management; school improvement and change; the role of leadership in professional development; the impact of technology; and the micropolitics of school leadership are important. Perhaps this concern has been prompted by the kind of concerns detailed by Murphy (2002, 2006). Other collections, such as Brent-Davies (2005), showcase the many leadership methods that are now part of the discourse in this field. These methods are strategic, transformational, inviting, ethical, learning-centered, constructivist, poetic, emotional, entrepreneurial, diffuse and sustainable.

More recent writings such as Starratt (2003) can see the emphasis on meaning, community, and mission that was lacking in previous studies. Marshall (2004), Larson and Murtadha (2002) and

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Bates (2006) associate educational leadership with social justice in their studies.

Lingard et al. (2003) and Mulford and colleagues (Mulford et al., 2004; Mulford, 2005) focused more on the importance of leadership and learning in their research. Both Starratt (2004) and Samier (2003) conduct new research on the moral foundations of effective leadership.

Gunter (2001, 2005) explores the tasks leading educators are expected to undertake in a Bourdieuan framework. Gronn (2003) explores the concept of designer leadership as well as the (selfish) new task of teachers. Samier and Bates (2006) rekindle interest in aesthetic concerns in executive leadership. Walker and Dimmock (2002) advocate a worldview that includes other cultures. The concept of educational leadership is discussed by Botry (2004) in the context of the global crisis. Beare (2000) argues that school leadership should be concerned with the long-term viability of the educational institution. Ribbins (2006) and colleagues examine once again the importance of history in the field of educational administration research. There are several extremely important links in all this current literature. Re-establishing the importance of leadership in promoting learning, this is the first change; secondly, this type of leadership is increasingly linked to the social, economic and political changes and demands of both localized and globalized societies, which is the second change; third, it seems that leadership is no longer focused on one person, but instead distributed across educational institutions as a shared responsibility; and fourth and perhaps most importantly, the mechanics of schooling are being rethought, which is the fourth change. It's safe to say that Dewey would approve of this. After all, the efforts spent in the last century in the study and practice of educational leadership have not been in vain.

Educational Leadership and Management as a Discipline

Van der Westhuizen and Prew (2006) express their regret at the "confusion and lack of agreement among academics and institutions about the exact nature of Educational Leadership and Management as a discipline". In their explanations on the subject, the authors state that although some academics see educational leadership and management as the same action or phenomenon, some separate the two disciplines and a third group emphasizes the connection between the two phenomena. All these perspectives are presented on the subject. This description of the state of the field is informative, but two sites on this topic highlight the nature of the uncertainty that exists.

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They use a wide variety of terms to express school management and leadership in a few hundred-word essay. The word "discipline" means, "What constitutes the discipline of Educational Leadership and Management?" seems to be their preferred expression, as in the question. It is possible to assume that they see this as a single action; yet they write about "a discipline such as educational administration" and "educational leadership, educational administration and policy disciplines", showing that they see it as three different types of activity. They also use other terminology for this purpose, such as 'fields' (meaning more than one field) and 'field' (meaning only one field). His confused thoughts can be seen elsewhere.

Even in the United Kingdom, where the epistemic community has traditionally shown little interest in theoretical issues, there has been much debate around the definition (Ribbins, 1999). According to Bush (1999:2), "differences arose as to whether educational administration should be seen as a 'field' or as a 'discipline'". Among the founding members of the United Kingdom, supporters of the 'field' name include Glatter, Hughes and Baron. Baron (1980:11) argues that as a result of this action, "educational administration as a field of research has very ill-defined boundaries". According to Hughes (1985:20), the book *Educational Administration and Social Sciences* by Baron and Taylor (1969) was an important early turning point in the growth of educational administration and administration in the UK as a field of study. Baron and Taylor were responsible for editing the book. "The approach taken was ... that educational administration is a field of practice and that its work should draw broadly, but selectively, from various fields of social science." According to Baron (1980:17), this stemmed from the political need to legitimize the study of educational administration... in the context of the University of London... Historically, educational studies were primarily divided into four subfields: philosophy of education; educational sociology and economics; Education psychology; and economics and economics of education.

The difficulty of stating the situation for some fields of study, such as educational administration, stems from the fact that emphasizing the contribution of disciplines in this setting is both necessary and desirable. Whatever may be said of Baron's argument, accepting the quotation in the previous sentence as it stands seems to compel him to consider educational administration as a field of study in its own right, which probably means that Baron should be distinguished.

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(1) *management,*

(2) *leadership and*

(3) *policy*

A study entitled "Reflections on the Field of Educational Administration Studies" by Fitz (1999: 314) sheds light on this particular aspect of the debate. He argues that different disciplines cannot be "reduced to one another," using the word "fields" to denote scientific fields, each with its own special interest and rules of access, privilege, and regulation. He uses the word "fields" to denote scientific arenas. One of the most important areas of study related to the concept of "area" is "areas of special interest" or the discourse that distinguishes one area from other neighboring or related areas..." To summarize my position on such matters, based on this and the other arguments cited above, I would argue that 'discipline' for analytical purposes ' (or form of knowledge) and 'field' (as in the field of knowledge) and that educational leadership, administration, management and policy of work (LAMP) is a mediated activity, or rather a field of knowledge, like the main field of education. That would be my position on such matters. From a philosophy's point of view, it should be distinguished from comparable fields such as curricular studies and development studies by its subject matter, that is, by what it studies rather than how it works.

(Hirst 1965; 1967) also deals with ideas, hypotheses, truth tests, and the like from a wide variety of fields of study or types of knowledge. Additionally, as Stenhouse (1975:1) explains, areas of specialization or research can be "theoretical" or "practical" in nature, " Hirst cites geography as an example of theoretical study and engineering ... as practical study." In the final analysis, it is justified to the extent that it facilitates the application and contributes to the further development of that application. Such a statement seems to imply that LAMP is a single domain, implying that the subdomains that then make up LAMP are not domains in themselves, or at least should not be treated as domains. It is possible to take this viewpoint, but there are risks, both in the real world and in philosophy, associated with any system that institutionalizes the extreme separation of these activities from one another.

Glatter (1987: 9-10), a few years ago I opposed the effort to create two separate and distinct disciplines of education policy and administration on the grounds that such a distinction was theoretically and practically unjustified. It recommends using both an administrative approach

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(Model A) and a managerial approach (Model B) in developing these concepts.

A theory like this rests obviously on the idea that management and leadership are two different and distinct types of endeavor. This point of view is not accepted by everyone. According to Glatter (1972:5) et al., there are many who think that the two names refer to more or less the same entity. Following Hodgkinson (1991:63-65), some people argue that they reflect two different but complementary sets of goals and actions. These perspectives seem to have more common ground on closer inspection than it might seem at first glance.

Consequently, according to Glatter (1972: 5), administration and management is "the process of securing decisions about what activities the organization will undertake and mobilizing human and material resources to undertake them." By associating these with "leadership", he takes positions that are not easily reconcilable, as at one point we see practically no distinction between "management" and "management", and at another point "we sometimes find" 'management' and sometimes 'management', in other words, more implying routine work but carries the greater meaning of steering or policy-making functions. This second inference suggests that there are two different levels of action, both of which are deeply rooted in the minds of the public, despite the fact that words are used differently, although not always consistently.

Hodgkinson, management is the application of philosophy in the real world. This is accomplished "through essentially abstract, philosophical, qualitative, strategic, and humanistic processes, and by nature concrete, practical, pragmatic, quantitative, and technological managerial processes" (1978: 8-9). This is achieved in the form of an ideal set of types in which management is constructed through three processes of philosophies, planning and politics, all of which can be 'under the heading of policy making'. Mobilizing, directing and monitoring are the three activities that are part of management, and taken together, these three processes can all be grouped under the heading of policy enforcement. For this analysis to be legitimate, it must have both theoretical and practical meaning. This is because in taxonomy... as opposed to just some kind of aesthetic order, if there is truth, then there must be truth. In my opinion, the most important reflections are those related to the training of managers and the sharing of managerial responsibilities within the organization (Hodgkinson, 1978:16-17).

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Failing, not being able to get it done, right people, not being aware of the stages and not being conscious and not communicating them means not firing at all six cylinders. It decides the administration as the appropriate expression for both the process of formulating policies and the actual implementation of those policies. Since administration systematically assimilates and develops management, and no group of activities can actually exist separately from another (1991:51), management is subordinate to and contained by the broader idea of administration. Management is both derived from and contained by management. Additionally, "there is a difference in usage between these words ... it depends to some extent on the semantic rules used.

Hodgkinson's (1991:53) argument that "the term can be used synonymously with administration" is obvious, though somewhat misleading. Burns (1978:2) compiles a list of more than one hundred key definitions of leadership based on this topic. According to Greenfield (1993:67-68), a significant amount of research ... with limiting and stagnant techniques ... a Brownie camera snapshot of a complex and incomprehensible process, as Cohen and March saw ... a skidding one. the wheel of the carriage: what the man is doing at that moment is of marginal importance compared to the other forces that put him in this situation in the first place and will largely determine the outcome. The idea of leadership, according to Hodgkinson (1991:49), "is not so frivolous as it is so volatile, insurmountable, incomprehensible, and misleading... which makes it very difficult to handle rigorously." Still, if we are to make valuable progress in understanding both the theory and practice of leadership, "there is no escape from grappling with the conceptual challenges involved." This requires recognizing that leadership encompasses "both management and management...". Consequently, leadership, when equated with management, can be seen as the process of putting policy, values, and philosophy into practice through the coordination of group efforts. It can be done successfully, horribly, or casually (1996:30). It is the process of directing personnel to goals through the organization. Such a definition emphasizes the fact that leadership, as well as being a leader, is more about what individuals do than who they are. However, its ambiguity leaves it open to a wide variety of rhetorical manipulations... It is a well-known fact that no school administrator who works for him will claim to have leadership qualities. Managers, on the other hand, tend to think of the function of leaders only in terms of definitions. Greenfield's assertion that leadership studies tend to focus on "the characteristics of leaders" when

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"their character matters" (Greenfield & Ribbins, 1993:259) has a major impact on both my perspective and the work I do.

While I share many of the above-mentioned issues, we see that Greenfield's claim also significantly influenced my work. Accordingly, Gunter and I have argued that there is an excessive amount of research on leadership in this area, but not enough research on leadership (detailed and contextual explanations of what individual leaders do and why they do it in a variety of specific circumstances) (Ribbins & Gunter, 2002: 362).

Conclusion and Recommendations

As a result, efforts to differentiate the basic terminology in the field have resulted in three conflicting perspectives. The first person from India after Sapre argues that the two concepts are incompatible. Following Glatter's work, another UK researcher claims they can be used interchangeably. The third theory, which emerged from North America after Hodgkinson, suggests that the two approaches are different but complementary. This situation is similar to Hodgkinson's, but it is difficult to be as convinced as he is that management and leadership are sometimes interchangeable terms. While I feel his narrative provides an illuminating agenda of what leaders must achieve in order to lead, we find it less helpful to explain how they went about achieving it. To do this, we go to the ideas of power-related concepts such as authority and influence. As a result, following Dahl (1957), French and Raven (1959) and Hemphill (1978), it is emphasized that while power is defined as the access to all the resources a leader can resort to, such access is not important. In this way we follow Dahl (1957), French and Raven (1959) and Hemphill (1978). A distinction must be made between acceptable power and unacceptable power (also known as "authority"). According to Ribbins (2005a), there is a sustainable and defensible type of leadership that emerges when influence and authority intersect. To address phenomena such as leadership (and management), it is necessary to have an understanding of the knowledge claims involved.

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